

$$R_{tt} = \ominus r^2 \left(\frac{df}{dz} \right)^2 + f^4 \left(\frac{dw}{dz} \right)^2 + r^2 f \cdot \left(\frac{d^2 f}{dz^2} \right) + r \cdot f \cdot \left(\frac{df}{dr} \right) \ominus r^2 \left(\frac{df}{dr} \right)^2 + f^4 \left(\frac{dw}{dr} \right)^2 + r^2 f \cdot \left(\frac{d^2 f}{dz^2} \right) \quad (1/2)$$

$$= f^4 \left[\left(\frac{dw}{dr} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{dw}{dz} \right)^2 \right] \ominus r^2 \left(\frac{df}{dz} \right)^2 + r^2 f \cdot \left(\frac{d^2 f}{dz^2} \right) + r f \left(\frac{df}{dr} \right) \ominus r^2 \left(\frac{df}{dr} \right)^2 + r^2 f \left(\frac{d^2 f}{dz^2} \right)$$

$$= \ominus r^2 \left[\left(\frac{df}{dz} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{df}{dr} \right)^2 \right] + r^2 f \left[\frac{d^2 f}{dz^2} + \frac{d^2 f}{dz^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{df}{dr} \right]$$

$$= f^4 \left[\left(\frac{dw}{dr} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{dw}{dz} \right)^2 \right] \ominus r^2 \left[\left(\frac{df}{dz} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{df}{dr} \right)^2 \right] + r^2 f \left[\frac{d^2 f}{dz^2} + \frac{d^2 f}{dz^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{df}{dr} \right] = e^{2\gamma} r^2 R_{tt}$$

$$R_{rz} = \frac{2r \cdot f^2}{2r \cdot f^2} \left(\frac{df}{dz} \right) \ominus \frac{r^2}{2r^2 f^2} \left(\frac{df}{dz} \right) \left(\frac{df}{dr} \right) + \frac{f^4 f^2}{2r^2 f^2} \left(\frac{dw}{dr} \right) \left(\frac{dw}{dz} \right) =$$

$$= \frac{1}{r} \left(\frac{df}{dz} \right) \ominus \frac{1}{2f^2} \left(\frac{df}{dr} \right) \left(\frac{df}{dz} \right) + \frac{f^2}{2r^2} \left(\frac{dw}{dr} \right) \left(\frac{dw}{dz} \right)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\boxed{R_{zz}} &= \ominus \frac{\cancel{r^2} f^2}{2r^2 \cancel{f^2}} \left(\frac{df}{dz} \right)^2 + \frac{f^4}{2r^2 \cancel{f^2}} \left(\frac{dw}{dz} \right)^2 + \frac{\cancel{r^2} f}{2r^2 \cancel{f^2}} \left(\frac{d^2 f}{dz^2} \right) \ominus \frac{\cancel{r^2} f^2}{2r^2 \cancel{f^2}} \left(\frac{d^2 y}{dz^2} \right) + \quad \left(\frac{2}{\text{cm}} \right) \\
&+ \frac{\cancel{r} \cdot f}{2r^2 \cancel{f^2}} \left(\frac{df}{dr} \right) \ominus \frac{\cancel{r^2}}{2r^2 \cancel{f^2}} \left(\frac{df}{dr} \right)^2 \ominus \frac{\cancel{2r} \cdot f^2}{2r^2 \cancel{f^2}} \left(\frac{dy}{dr} \right) + \frac{\cancel{r^2} \cdot f}{2r^2 \cancel{f^2}} \left(\frac{d^2 f}{dr^2} \right) \ominus \frac{\cancel{2r^2} f^2}{2r^2 \cancel{f^2}} \left(\frac{d^2 y}{dr^2} \right) \\
&= \ominus \frac{1}{f^2} \left(\frac{df}{dz} \right)^2 + \frac{f^2}{2r^2} \left(\frac{dw}{dz} \right)^2 + \frac{1}{2f} \left(\frac{d^2 f}{dz^2} \right) \ominus \left(\frac{d^2 y}{dz^2} \right) + \frac{1}{2rf} \left(\frac{df}{dr} \right) \ominus \frac{1}{2f^2} \left(\frac{df}{dr} \right)^2 \ominus \frac{1}{r} \frac{dy}{dr} + \frac{1}{2f} \left(\frac{d^2 f}{dr^2} \right) \ominus \frac{d^2 y}{dr^2} = \\
&= \ominus \left[\frac{d^2 y}{dr^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{dy}{dr} + \frac{d^2 y}{dz^2} \right] + \frac{f^2}{2r^2} \left(\frac{dw}{dz} \right)^2 \ominus \frac{1}{f^2} \left(\frac{df}{dz} \right)^2 + \frac{1}{2f} \left(\frac{d^2 f}{dz^2} \right) + \frac{1}{2rf} \left(\frac{df}{dr} \right) \ominus \frac{1}{2f^2} \left(\frac{df}{dr} \right)^2 + \frac{1}{2f} \left(\frac{d^2 f}{dr^2} \right) = \\
&= \ominus \left[\frac{d^2 y}{dr^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{dy}{dr} + \frac{d^2 y}{dz^2} \right] + \frac{f^2}{2r^2} \left(\frac{dw}{dz} \right)^2 + \frac{1}{2f} \left[\frac{d^2 f}{dz^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{df}{dr} + \frac{d^2 f}{dr^2} \right] \ominus \frac{1}{f^2} \left(\frac{df}{dz} \right)^2 \ominus \frac{1}{2f^2} \left(\frac{df}{dr} \right)^2
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Riem} = & \ominus \frac{1}{2r^2} \left(\frac{df}{dz} \right)^2 \cdot \frac{1}{2r^2 f^2} + \frac{r^2 \cdot f}{2r^2 \cdot f^2} \left(\frac{d^2 f}{dz^2} \right) \ominus \frac{2r^2 \cdot f^2}{2r^2 \cdot f^2} \left(\frac{dy}{dz^2} \right) + \frac{r \cdot f}{2r^2 \cdot f^2} \left(\frac{df}{dr} \right) \ominus \frac{2r^2}{2r^2} \left(\frac{df}{dr} \right)^2 \cdot \frac{1}{2r^2 \cdot f^2} + \frac{3}{\text{cur}} \\
 & + \frac{2r \cdot f^2}{2r^2 \cdot f^2} \left(\frac{dy}{dr} \right) + \frac{f^2 \left(\frac{dw}{dr} \right)^2}{2r^2 \cdot f^2} + \frac{r^2 \cdot f}{2r^2 \cdot f^2} \left(\frac{d^2 f}{dr^2} \right) \ominus \frac{2r^2 \cdot f^2}{2r^2 \cdot f^2} \left(\frac{d^2 y}{dr^2} \right) = \\
 & \ominus \frac{1}{r} \quad = \frac{f^2}{2r^2} \quad = \frac{1}{2f}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 = & \left(\frac{d^2 y}{dz^2} \right) \ominus \left(\frac{d^2 y}{dr^2} \right) + \frac{1}{r} \frac{dy}{dr} \ominus \frac{1}{2f^2} \left(\frac{df}{dz} \right)^2 + \frac{1}{2f} \left(\frac{d^2 f}{dz^2} \right) + \frac{1}{2rf} \left(\frac{df}{dr} \right) \ominus \frac{1}{f^2} \left(\frac{df}{dr} \right)^2 + \\
 & + \frac{f^2}{2r^2} \left(\frac{dw}{dr} \right)^2 + \frac{1}{2f} \left(\frac{d^2 f}{dr^2} \right) = \frac{1}{r} \frac{dy}{dr} \ominus \frac{d^2 y}{dr^2} \ominus \frac{d^2 y}{dz^2} + \frac{f^2}{2r^2} \left(\frac{dw}{dr} \right)^2 + \\
 & + \frac{1}{2f} \left[\frac{d^2 f}{dz^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{df}{dr} + \frac{d^2 f}{dr^2} \right] \ominus \frac{1}{2f^2} \left(\frac{df}{dz} \right)^2 \ominus \frac{1}{f^2} \left(\frac{df}{dr} \right)^2
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{RHS} \cdot e^{2\gamma} r^2 = r^2 \omega(r,z) \left(\frac{df}{dz}\right)^2 \ominus 2r^2 f \cdot \left(\frac{df}{dz}\right) \left(\frac{d\omega}{dz}\right) \ominus f^4 \cdot \omega \cdot \left(\frac{d\omega}{dz}\right)^2 \ominus r^2 f \cdot \omega \cdot \left(\frac{d^2 f}{dz^2}\right) +$$

$$\ominus r^2 f^2 \cdot \left(\frac{d^2 \omega}{dz^2}\right) \ominus r f \cdot \omega \cdot \left(\frac{df}{dz}\right) + r^2 \omega \cdot \left(\frac{df}{dr}\right)^2 + r f^2 \cdot \left(\frac{d\omega}{dr}\right) \ominus 2r^2 f \cdot \left(\frac{df}{dr}\right) \left(\frac{d\omega}{dr}\right) +$$

$$\ominus f^4 \cdot \omega \cdot \left(\frac{d\omega}{dr}\right)^2 \ominus r^2 f \cdot \omega \cdot \left(\frac{d^2 f}{dr^2}\right) \ominus r^2 f^2 \cdot \left(\frac{d^2 \omega}{dr^2}\right)$$

$\frac{4}{c^2}$

$$ds^2 = \ominus f(r,z) [dt \ominus \omega(r,z) d\phi]^2 + \frac{1}{f(r,z)} [e^{2\gamma(r,z)} (dr^2 + dz^2)] + \frac{r^2}{f(r,z)} d\phi^2$$

$$g_{rr} = \frac{e^{2\gamma}}{f}$$

$$g_{zz} = \frac{e^{2\gamma}}{f}$$

$$g_{\phi\phi} = \frac{r^2}{f} \ominus f \cdot \omega^2$$

$$g_{\phi t} = f \cdot \omega$$

$$g_{tt} = \ominus f$$

$$\text{let } g = \ominus \frac{r^2 e^{4\gamma}}{f^2}$$

$$g^{rr} = \frac{f}{e^{2\gamma}}$$

$$g^{zz} = \frac{f}{e^{2\gamma}}$$

$$g^{\phi\phi} = \frac{f}{r^2}$$

$$g^{\phi t} = \frac{f \cdot \omega}{r^2}$$

$$g^{tt} = \frac{\ominus r^2 + f \cdot \omega^2}{r^2 \cdot f}$$

$$\boxed{R_{rr}} = \frac{1}{r} \frac{dy}{dr} \ominus \frac{dy^2}{dr^2} \ominus \frac{dy^2}{dz^2} + \frac{f^2}{2r^2} \left(\frac{dw}{dr} \right)^2 + \frac{1}{2f} \left[\frac{d^2 f}{dz^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{df}{dr} + \frac{d^2 f}{dr^2} \right] \ominus \frac{1}{2f^2} \left(\frac{df}{dz} \right)^2 \ominus \frac{1}{f^2} \left(\frac{df}{dr} \right)^2 \quad (5/cwr)$$

$$\boxed{R_{zz}} = \ominus \left[\frac{dy}{dr} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{dy}{dr} + \frac{dy^2}{dz^2} \right] + \frac{f^2}{2r^2} \left(\frac{dw}{dz} \right)^2 + \frac{1}{2f} \left[\frac{d^2 f}{dz^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{df}{dr} + \frac{d^2 f}{dr^2} \right] \ominus \frac{1}{f^2} \left(\frac{df}{dz} \right)^2 \ominus \frac{1}{2f^2} \left(\frac{df}{dr} \right)^2$$

$$\boxed{R_{rz}} = \frac{1}{r} \left(\frac{dy}{dz} \right) \ominus \frac{1}{2f^2} \left(\frac{df}{dr} \right) \left(\frac{df}{dz} \right) + \frac{f^2}{2r^2} \left(\frac{dw}{dr} \right) \left(\frac{dw}{dz} \right)$$

$$\boxed{e^{2\gamma} r^2 R_{tt}} = f^4 \left[\left(\frac{dw}{dr} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{dw}{dz} \right)^2 \right] \ominus r^2 \left[\left(\frac{df}{dz} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{df}{dr} \right)^2 \right] + r^2 f \left[\frac{d^2 f}{dr^2} + \frac{d^2 f}{dz^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{df}{dr} \right]$$

6/ans

$$R_{rr} \ominus R_{zz} = \frac{1}{r} \frac{dy}{dr} \ominus \frac{d^2y}{dr^2} \ominus \frac{d^2y}{dz^2} \oplus \frac{f^2}{2r^2} \left(\frac{dw}{dr} \right)^2 + \frac{1}{2f} [] \ominus \frac{1}{2f^2} \left(\frac{df}{dz} \right)^2 \oplus \frac{1}{f^2} \left(\frac{df}{dr} \right)^2 +$$

$$+ \frac{d^2y}{dr^2} \oplus \frac{1}{r} \frac{dy}{dr} + \frac{d^2y}{dz^2} \ominus \frac{f^2}{2r^2} \left(\frac{dw}{dz} \right)^2 \ominus \frac{1}{2f} [] + \frac{1}{f} \left(\frac{df}{dz} \right)^2 + \frac{1}{2f^2} \left(\frac{df}{dr} \right)^2 =$$

$$= \frac{2}{r} \frac{dy}{dr} + \frac{f^2}{2r^2} \left[\left(\frac{dw}{dr} \right)^2 \ominus \left(\frac{dw}{dz} \right)^2 \right] + \frac{1}{2f^2} \left(\frac{df}{dz} \right)^2 \ominus \frac{1}{2f^2} \left(\frac{df}{dr} \right)^2 =$$

$$= \frac{2}{r} \frac{dy}{dr} + \frac{f^2}{2r^2} \left[\left(\frac{dw}{dr} \right)^2 \ominus \left(\frac{dw}{dz} \right)^2 \right] + \frac{1}{2f^2} \left[\left(\frac{df}{dz} \right)^2 \ominus \left(\frac{df}{dr} \right)^2 \right]$$

$$R_{rr} + R_{zz} = \frac{1}{r} \frac{dy}{dr} \ominus \frac{d^2y}{dr^2} \ominus \frac{d^2y}{dz^2} + \frac{f^2}{2r^2} \left(\frac{dw}{dr} \right)^2 + \frac{1}{2f} [] \ominus \frac{1}{2f^2} \left(\frac{df}{dz} \right)^2 \ominus \frac{1}{f^2} \left(\frac{df}{dr} \right)^2$$

$$\ominus \frac{d^2y}{dr^2} \oplus \frac{1}{r} \frac{dy}{dr} \oplus \frac{d^2y}{dz^2} + \frac{f^2}{2r^2} \left(\frac{dw}{dz} \right)^2 + \frac{1}{2f} [] \ominus \frac{1}{f^2} \left(\frac{df}{dz} \right)^2 \ominus \frac{1}{2f^2} \left(\frac{df}{dr} \right)^2 =$$

$$= \ominus 2 \left[\frac{d^2y}{dr^2} + \frac{d^2y}{dz^2} \right] + \frac{f^2}{2r^2} \left[\left(\frac{dw}{dr} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{dw}{dz} \right)^2 \right] + \frac{1}{f} [] \ominus \frac{3}{2f^2} \left(\frac{df}{dz} \right)^2 \ominus \frac{3}{2f^2} \left(\frac{df}{dr} \right)^2$$

$$e^{2\gamma} r^2 R_{tt} = f^4 \left[\left(\frac{dw}{dr} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{dw}{dz} \right)^2 \right] \ominus r^2 \left[\left(\frac{df}{dr} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{df}{dz} \right)^2 \right] + r^2 f \left[\frac{d^2 f}{dr^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{df}{dr} + \frac{d^2 f}{dz^2} \right] : r^2 f^2$$

$$\frac{e^{2\gamma} r^2 R_{tt}}{r^2 f^2} = \frac{f^2}{r^2} \left[\left(\frac{dw}{dr} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{dw}{dz} \right)^2 \right] \ominus \frac{1}{f^2} \left[\left(\frac{df}{dr} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{df}{dz} \right)^2 \right] + \frac{1}{f} \left[\frac{d^2 f}{dr^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{df}{dr} + \frac{d^2 f}{dz^2} \right]$$

$\frac{7}{arr}$

$$\frac{1}{f} \left[\right] = \frac{e^{2\gamma} r^2 R_{tt}}{f^2 r^2} \ominus \frac{f^2}{r^2} \left[\left(\frac{dw}{dr} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{dw}{dz} \right)^2 \right] + \frac{1}{f^2} \left[\left(\frac{df}{dz} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{df}{dr} \right)^2 \right]$$

$$R_{rr} + R_{zz} = \ominus 2 \left[\frac{d^2 \gamma}{dr^2} + \frac{d^2 \gamma}{dz^2} \right] + \frac{f^2}{2r^2} \left[\left(\frac{dw}{dr} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{dw}{dz} \right)^2 \right] + \frac{1}{f} \left[\right] \ominus \frac{3}{2f^2} \left[\left(\frac{df}{dz} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{df}{dr} \right)^2 \right]$$

$$= \ominus \frac{f^2}{2r^2} \left[\left(\frac{dw}{dr} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{dw}{dz} \right)^2 \right]$$

$$R_{rr} + R_{zz} = \ominus 2 \left[\frac{d^2 \gamma}{dr^2} + \frac{d^2 \gamma}{dz^2} \right] + \frac{f^2}{2r^2} \left[\left(\frac{dw}{dr} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{dw}{dz} \right)^2 \right] + \frac{e^{2\gamma} R_{tt}}{f^2} \ominus \frac{f^2}{r^2} \left[\left(\frac{dw}{dr} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{dw}{dz} \right)^2 \right] +$$

$$+ \frac{1}{f^2} \left[\left(\frac{df}{dz} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{df}{dr} \right)^2 \right] \ominus \frac{3}{2f^2} \left[\left(\frac{df}{dz} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{df}{dr} \right)^2 \right]$$

$$= \ominus \frac{1}{2f^2} \left[\left(\frac{df}{dz} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{df}{dr} \right)^2 \right]$$

$$R_{rr} + R_{zz} \ominus \frac{e^{2\gamma} R_{tt}}{f^2} = \ominus 2 \left[\frac{d^2 \gamma}{dr^2} + \frac{d^2 \gamma}{dz^2} \right] \ominus \frac{1}{2f^2} \left[\left(\frac{df}{dz} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{df}{dr} \right)^2 \right] \ominus \frac{f^2}{2r^2} \left[\left(\frac{dw}{dr} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{dw}{dz} \right)^2 \right]$$

$$\ominus \frac{1}{2} [R_{rr} + R_{zz}] + \frac{e^{2\gamma} R_{tt}}{2f^2} = \left(\frac{d^2 \gamma}{dr^2} + \frac{d^2 \gamma}{dz^2} \right) + \frac{1}{4f^2} \left[\left(\frac{df}{dz} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{df}{dr} \right)^2 \right] + \frac{f^2}{4r^2} \left[\left(\frac{dw}{dr} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{dw}{dz} \right)^2 \right]$$

8/curr

$$R_{rr} \ominus R_{zz} = \frac{2}{r} \frac{d\gamma}{dr} + \frac{f^2}{2r^2} \left[\left(\frac{dw}{dr} \right)^2 \ominus \left(\frac{dw}{dz} \right)^2 \right] + \frac{1}{2f^2} \left[\left(\frac{df}{dz} \right)^2 \ominus \left(\frac{df}{dr} \right)^2 \right]$$

$$R_{rz} = \frac{1}{r} \left(\frac{d\gamma}{dz} \right) \ominus \frac{1}{2f^2} \left(\frac{df}{dr} \right) \left(\frac{df}{dz} \right) + \frac{f^2}{2r^2} \left(\frac{dw}{dr} \right) \left(\frac{dw}{dz} \right)$$

$$e^{2\gamma} r^2 R_{tt} = f^4 \left[\left(\frac{dw}{dz} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{dw}{dr} \right)^2 \right] \ominus r^2 \left[\left(\frac{df}{dz} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{df}{dr} \right)^2 \right] + r^2 f \left[\frac{d^2 f}{dr^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{df}{dr} + \frac{d^2 f}{dz^2} \right]$$

$$\nabla \psi = \vec{e}_1 \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \rho} + \vec{e}_2 \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \phi} + \vec{e}_3 \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial z}$$

$$\vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{A} = \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial}{\partial \rho} (\rho A_1) + \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial A_2}{\partial \phi} + \frac{\partial A_3}{\partial z}$$

$$\nabla^2 \psi = \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial}{\partial \rho} \left(\rho \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial \rho} \right) + \frac{1}{\rho^2} \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial \phi^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \psi}{\partial z^2}$$

Cylindrische coördinaten (ρ, ϕ, z)

$$\vec{\nabla} \times \vec{A} = \vec{e}_1 \left[\frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial A_3}{\partial \phi} \ominus \frac{\partial A_2}{\partial z} \right] + \vec{e}_2 \left[\frac{\partial A_1}{\partial z} \ominus \frac{\partial A_3}{\partial \rho} \right] + \vec{e}_3 \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial \rho} (\rho A_2) \ominus \frac{\partial A_1}{\partial \phi} \right]$$

$$G_{rr} = r^2 \left(\frac{df}{dz}\right)^2 \frac{1}{4r^2 f^2} \ominus \frac{f^4}{4r^2 f^2} \left(\frac{dw}{dz}\right)^2 \ominus \frac{r^2}{4r^2 f^2} \left(\frac{df}{dr}\right)^2 + \frac{4rf^2}{4r^2 f^2} \left(\frac{dy}{dr}\right) + \frac{f^4}{4r^2 f^2} \left(\frac{dw}{dr}\right)^2 =$$

$$= \left[\frac{1}{4f^2} \left(\frac{df}{dz}\right)^2 \ominus \frac{f^2}{4r^2} \left(\frac{dw}{dz}\right)^2 \ominus \frac{1}{4f^2} \left(\frac{df}{dr}\right)^2 + \frac{1}{r} \left(\frac{dy}{dr}\right) + \frac{f^2}{4r^2} \left(\frac{dw}{dr}\right)^2 \right]$$

$$G_{zz} = \ominus \frac{r^2}{4r^2 f^2} \left(\frac{df}{dz}\right)^2 + \frac{f^4}{4r^2 f^2} \left(\frac{dw}{dz}\right)^2 + \frac{r^2}{4r^2 f^2} \left(\frac{df}{dr}\right)^2 \ominus \frac{4rf^2}{4r^2 f^2} \left(\frac{dy}{dr}\right) \ominus \frac{f^4}{4r^2 f^2} \left(\frac{dw}{dr}\right)^2 =$$

$$= \left[\ominus \frac{1}{4f^2} \left(\frac{df}{dz}\right)^2 + \frac{f^2}{4r^2} \left(\frac{dw}{dz}\right)^2 + \frac{1}{4f^2} \left(\frac{df}{dr}\right)^2 \ominus \frac{1}{r} \left(\frac{dy}{dr}\right) \ominus \frac{f^2}{4r^2} \left(\frac{dw}{dr}\right)^2 \right]$$

$$G_{rz} = \frac{2rf^2}{2r^2 f^2} \left(\frac{dy}{dz}\right) \ominus \frac{r^2}{2r^2 f^2} \left(\frac{df}{dz}\right) \left(\frac{df}{dr}\right) + \frac{f^4}{2r^2 f^2} \left(\frac{dw}{dz}\right) \left(\frac{dw}{dr}\right) =$$

$$= \left[\frac{1}{r} \left(\frac{dy}{dz}\right) \ominus \frac{1}{2f^2} \left(\frac{df}{dz}\right) \left(\frac{df}{dr}\right) + \frac{f^2}{2r^2} \left(\frac{dw}{dz}\right) \left(\frac{dw}{dr}\right) \right]$$

$$G_{tt} = \ominus 5r^2 \left(\frac{df}{dz}\right)^2 \cancel{f^2} \oplus 3f^4 \left(\frac{dw}{dz}\right)^2 + 4r^2 f \frac{d^2 f}{dz^2} \ominus 4r^2 f^2 \left(\frac{d^2 y}{dz^2}\right) \oplus 4rf \left(\frac{df}{dr}\right) \ominus 5r^2 \left(\frac{df}{dr}\right)^2 +$$

$$+ 3f^4 \left(\frac{dw}{dr}\right)^2 + 4r^2 f \left(\frac{d^2 f}{dr^2}\right) \ominus 4r^2 f^2 \left(\frac{d^2 y}{dr^2}\right) = \ominus 5r^2 \left[\left(\frac{df}{dz}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{df}{dr}\right)^2 \right] + 3f^4 \left[\left(\frac{dw}{dr}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{dw}{dz}\right)^2 \right] +$$

$$+ 4r^2 f \left[\frac{d^2 f}{dz^2} + \frac{1}{r} \frac{df}{dr} + \frac{d^2 f}{dr^2} \right] \ominus 4r^2 f^2 \left[\left(\frac{d^2 y}{dr^2}\right) + \left(\frac{d^2 y}{dz^2}\right) \right]$$

$$\boxed{F_m F_m} = \left(\frac{2\Theta\alpha}{4}\right) (F_m \ominus B_m) (F_m \ominus B_m) = \frac{2\Theta\alpha}{4} [F_m F_m \ominus 2B_m F_m + B_m B_m] \quad (1)$$

$$\boxed{\tilde{B}_m \tilde{B}_m} = \left(\frac{2\Theta\alpha}{4}\right) (F_m + B_m) (F_m \oplus B_m) = \frac{2\Theta\alpha}{4} [F_m F_m + 2B_m F_m + B_m B_m]$$

$$\boxed{\tilde{F}_m \tilde{F}_m} = \left(\frac{2\Theta\alpha}{4}\right) [F_m \ominus B_m] [F_m \ominus B_m] = \left(\frac{2\Theta\alpha}{4}\right) [F_m F_m \ominus F_m B_m \ominus B_m F_m + B_m B_m]$$

$$\boxed{\tilde{B}_m \tilde{B}_m} = \left(\frac{2\Theta\alpha}{4}\right) [F_m + B_m] [F_m \oplus B_m] = \left(\frac{2\Theta\alpha}{4}\right) [F_m F_m + B_m F_m + F_m B_m + B_m B_m]$$

$$\boxed{\Pi_m(F)} = \left[\frac{1}{2} \tilde{F}_m \tilde{F}_m \ominus \frac{1}{8} g_m F^2 \right] = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{2\Theta\alpha}{4}\right) [F_m F_m \ominus F_m B_m \ominus B_m F_m + B_m B_m] +$$

$$\ominus \frac{1}{8} g_m [F_m F_m \ominus 2F_m B_m + B_m B_m] \left(\frac{2\Theta\alpha}{4}\right) =$$

$$= \left(\frac{2\Theta\alpha}{4}\right) \left[\frac{1}{2} F_m F_m \ominus \frac{1}{2} F_m B_m \ominus \frac{1}{2} B_m F_m + \frac{1}{2} B_m B_m \right] \ominus \frac{1}{8} g_m (F_m F_m) \ominus \frac{1}{8} g_m (B_m B_m) + \frac{1}{8} g_m [2F_m B_m] =$$

$$= \left(\frac{2\Theta\alpha}{4}\right) \left\{ \frac{1}{2} F_m F_m \ominus \frac{1}{8} g_m F^2 + \frac{1}{2} B_m B_m \ominus \frac{1}{8} g_m B^2 \ominus \frac{1}{2} F_m B_m \ominus \frac{1}{2} B_m F_m \ominus \frac{1}{8} g_m [2F_m B_m] \right\}$$

$$= \left(\frac{2\Theta\alpha}{4}\right) \left[\Pi_m(F) + \Pi_m(B) \ominus \frac{1}{2} F_m B_m \ominus \frac{1}{2} B_m F_m \ominus \frac{1}{4} g_m F_m B_m \right] \leftarrow \Pi_m(\tilde{F})$$

$$\boxed{\Pi_{\mu\nu}(\tilde{B})} = \left[\frac{1}{2} \tilde{B}_{\mu\sigma} \cdot \tilde{B}_{\nu}{}^{\sigma} \ominus \frac{1}{8} g_{\mu\nu} \tilde{B}^2 \right] = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{2+d}{4} \right) \left[\underline{F_{\mu\sigma} F_{\nu}{}^{\sigma}} + \underline{B_{\mu\sigma} \cdot B_{\nu}{}^{\sigma}} + \underline{F_{\mu\sigma} B_{\nu}{}^{\sigma}} + \underline{B_{\mu\sigma} B_{\nu}{}^{\sigma}} \right] +$$

$$\ominus \frac{1}{8} g_{\mu\nu} \left[\underline{F_{\alpha\beta} F^{\alpha\beta}} + 2 \underline{F_{\alpha\beta} B^{\alpha\beta}} + \underline{B_{\alpha\beta} B^{\alpha\beta}} \right] \left(\frac{2+d}{4} \right) =$$

$$= \left(\frac{2+d}{4} \right) \left\{ \underbrace{\frac{1}{2} F_{\mu\sigma} F_{\nu}{}^{\sigma} \ominus \frac{1}{8} g_{\mu\nu} F_{\alpha\beta} F^{\alpha\beta}}_{\Pi_{\mu\nu}(F)} + \underbrace{\frac{1}{2} B_{\mu\sigma} \cdot B_{\nu}{}^{\sigma} \ominus \frac{1}{8} g_{\mu\nu} B_{\alpha\beta} B^{\alpha\beta}}_{\Pi_{\mu\nu}(B)} + \right.$$

$$\left. + \frac{1}{2} B_{\mu\sigma} \cdot B_{\nu}{}^{\sigma} + \frac{1}{2} F_{\mu\sigma} B_{\nu}{}^{\sigma} \ominus \frac{1}{8} g_{\mu\nu} (2 F_{\alpha\beta} B^{\alpha\beta}) \right\} =$$

$$= \frac{2+d}{4} \left[\underbrace{\Pi_{\mu\nu}(F) + \Pi_{\mu\nu}(B)}_{\text{circled}} \oplus \frac{1}{2} B_{\mu\sigma} B_{\nu}{}^{\sigma} + \frac{1}{2} F_{\mu\sigma} B_{\nu}{}^{\sigma} \ominus \frac{1}{8} g_{\mu\nu} F_{\alpha\beta} B^{\alpha\beta} \right]$$

② $\Pi_{\mu\nu} = \frac{\ominus \partial S(F)}{\partial g^{\mu\nu}}$

$\Pi_{\mu\nu}(F, B, \alpha F \beta) \neq \Pi_{\mu\nu}(F) + \Pi_{\mu\nu}(B)$

$\frac{\partial S}{\partial A_m} = 0 \Rightarrow \alpha$ nicht da

$\frac{\partial S}{\partial B_m} = 0 \Rightarrow$ derivative weg

$\tilde{A}_m = \square, \tilde{B}_m = \square$

$$\boxed{\Pi_{\mu\nu}(F) + \Pi_{\mu\nu}(\tilde{B})} = \left(\frac{2+d}{4} \right) \left[\Pi_{\mu\nu}(F) + \Pi_{\mu\nu}(B) \right] + \left(\frac{2+d}{4} \right) \left[\Pi_{\mu\nu}(F) + \Pi_{\mu\nu}(B) \right] +$$

$$+ \left(\frac{2+d}{4} \right) \left[\ominus \frac{1}{2} F_{\mu\sigma} B_{\nu}{}^{\sigma} \ominus \frac{1}{2} B_{\mu\sigma} F_{\nu}{}^{\sigma} \ominus \frac{1}{8} g_{\mu\nu} F_{\alpha\beta} B^{\alpha\beta} \right] + \left(\frac{2+d}{4} \right) \left[\frac{1}{2} B_{\mu\sigma} \cdot F_{\nu}{}^{\sigma} + \frac{1}{2} F_{\mu\sigma} B_{\nu}{}^{\sigma} \ominus \frac{1}{8} g_{\mu\nu} F_{\alpha\beta} B^{\alpha\beta} \right] =$$

$$= \frac{1}{2} \left[\Pi_{\mu\nu}(F) + \Pi_{\mu\nu}(B) \right] + \frac{1}{2} \left[\Pi_{\mu\nu}(F) + \Pi_{\mu\nu}(B) \right] +$$

$$+ \frac{1}{2} [0] = \text{circled } \Pi_{\mu\nu}(F) + \Pi_{\mu\nu}(B)$$

$$\tilde{A}_m = a(A_m \ominus B_m) / b \quad \tilde{A}_m = a(A_m \ominus B_m) / (ab)$$

$$\tilde{B}_m = b(A_m + B_m) / a \quad \tilde{B}_m = b(A_m + B_m) / (ab)$$

$$b\tilde{A}_m + a\tilde{B}_m = (a+b)A_m + (b-a)B_m = abA_m \ominus abB_m + baA_m + baB_m =$$

$$\frac{b\tilde{A}_m + a\tilde{B}_m}{2ab} = A_m$$

$$\ominus b\tilde{A}_m \oplus a\tilde{B}_m = \ominus abA_m + baB_m \oplus baA_m \oplus abB_m = 2abA_m$$

$$\frac{\ominus b\tilde{A}_m \oplus a\tilde{B}_m}{2ab} = A_m$$

(1/A)

$$\tilde{A}_m = \frac{\sqrt{2\ominus\alpha}}{2} (A_m \ominus B_m)$$

$$\nabla_m \tilde{A}_v = \frac{\sqrt{2\ominus\alpha}}{2} (\nabla_m A_v \ominus \nabla_m B_v)$$

$$\tilde{B}_m = \frac{\sqrt{2+\alpha}}{2} (A_m + B_m)$$

$$\nabla_m \tilde{B}_v = \frac{\sqrt{2+\alpha}}{2} (\nabla_m A_v + \nabla_m B_v)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{F}_{mv} &= \nabla_m \tilde{A}_v \ominus \nabla_v \tilde{A}_m = \frac{\sqrt{2\ominus\alpha}}{2} [(\nabla_m A_v \ominus \nabla_m B_v) \ominus (\nabla_v A_m \ominus \nabla_v B_m)] = \\ &= \frac{\sqrt{2\ominus\alpha}}{2} [(\nabla_m A_v \ominus \nabla_v A_m) \ominus (\nabla_m B_v \ominus \nabla_v B_m)] = \frac{\sqrt{2\ominus\alpha}}{2} (F_{mv} \ominus B_{mv}) \end{aligned}$$

$$\tilde{B}_{mv} = \nabla_m \tilde{B}_v \ominus \nabla_v \tilde{B}_m = \frac{\sqrt{2+\alpha}}{2} [(\nabla_m A_v + \nabla_m B_v) \ominus (\nabla_v A_m + \nabla_v B_m)] = \frac{\sqrt{2+\alpha}}{2} (F_{mv} + B_{mv})$$

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{F}_{mv} \tilde{F}^{mv} &= \frac{(2\ominus\alpha)}{4} [(F_{mv} \ominus B_{mv})(F^{mv} \ominus B^{mv})] = \frac{(2\ominus\alpha)}{4} [F_{mv} F^{mv} \ominus B_{mv} F^{mv} \ominus F_{mv} B^{mv} + B_{mv} B^{mv}] = \\ &= \frac{2\ominus\alpha}{4} [F_{mv} F^{mv} \ominus 2B_{mv} F^{mv} + B_{mv} B^{mv}] \end{aligned}$$

$$\tilde{B}_{mv} \tilde{B}^{mv} = \frac{2+\alpha}{4} [(F_{mv} + B_{mv})(F^{mv} + B^{mv})] = \frac{2+\alpha}{4} [F_{mv} F^{mv} + 2B_{mv} F^{mv} + B_{mv} B^{mv}]$$

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{F}_{mv} \tilde{F}^{mv} + \tilde{B}_{mv} \tilde{B}^{mv} &= \frac{(2\ominus\alpha)}{4} F_{mv} F^{mv} \ominus \frac{(2-\alpha)}{4} \cdot 2 \cdot B_{mv} F^{mv} + \frac{2\ominus\alpha}{4} B_{mv} B^{mv} + \\ &+ \frac{2+\alpha}{4} F_{mv} F^{mv} + \frac{(2+\alpha)}{4} \cdot 2 \cdot B_{mv} F^{mv} + \frac{2+\alpha}{4} B_{mv} B^{mv} = F_{mv} F^{mv} + B_{mv} B^{mv} + \\ &+ \frac{1}{2} (2+\alpha \ominus 2-\alpha) = \alpha F_{mv} B^{mv} + F_{mv} F^{mv} + B_{mv} B^{mv} \end{aligned}$$

$$S_m = \int d^4x \sqrt{|g|} (F_{\alpha\beta} F_{\gamma\delta} g^{\alpha\gamma} g^{\beta\delta})$$

2/A

$$\begin{aligned} \delta_g S_m &= \int d^4x \left[\frac{1}{2} \sqrt{|g|} g_{ij} \delta g^{ij} F^2 \right] + \int d^4x \sqrt{|g|} \left[F_{\alpha\beta} F_{\gamma\delta} \delta g^{\alpha\gamma} g^{\beta\delta} + F_{\alpha\beta} F_{\gamma\delta} g^{\alpha\gamma} \delta g^{\beta\delta} \right] = \\ &= \int d^4x \sqrt{|g|} \left[\frac{1}{2} g_{ij} \delta g^{ij} F^2 + F_{\alpha}{}^{\delta} F_{\gamma}{}^{\delta} \delta g^{\alpha\gamma} + F_{\alpha}{}^{\delta} F_{\delta}{}^{\gamma} \delta g^{\alpha\gamma} \right] = \\ &= \int d^4x \sqrt{|g|} \left[2 F_{\alpha}{}^{\delta} F_{\delta}{}^{\gamma} \delta g^{\alpha\gamma} + \frac{1}{2} g_{\alpha\beta} F^2 \delta g^{\alpha\beta} \right] = \int d^4x \sqrt{|g|} \left(2 F_{\alpha}{}^{\delta} F_{\delta}{}^{\gamma} + \frac{1}{2} g_{\alpha\beta} F_{\mu\nu} F^{\mu\nu} \right) \delta g^{\alpha\beta} \end{aligned}$$

$$\frac{\delta S_m}{\sqrt{|g|} \delta g^{\alpha\beta}} = T_{\alpha\beta}$$

$$S_m = \int d^4x \sqrt{|g|} \left(\frac{1}{2} F_{\mu\nu} F^{\mu\nu} + \frac{1}{2} \tilde{F}_{\mu\nu} \tilde{B}^{\mu\nu} \right)$$

$$\frac{\delta S_m(F)}{\sqrt{|g|} \delta g^{\alpha\beta}} \doteq T_{\alpha\beta}(F)$$

$$\frac{\delta S_m(\tilde{B})}{\sqrt{|g|} \delta g^{\alpha\beta}} \doteq T_{\alpha\beta}(\tilde{B})$$

because we have $\ominus$ in the action!

$$T_{\alpha\beta}(F) \doteq 2 F_{\alpha}{}^{\delta} F_{\delta}{}^{\gamma} + \frac{1}{2} g_{\alpha\beta} F^2$$

$$T_{\alpha\beta}(\tilde{B}) \doteq 2 \tilde{B}_{\alpha}{}^{\delta} \tilde{B}_{\delta}{}^{\gamma} + \frac{1}{2} g_{\alpha\beta} \tilde{B}^2$$

$$\boxed{\nabla_m F^{mt} = 0}$$

$$\partial_m [\sqrt{-g}] F^{mt} = 0$$

(A/1)

$$\partial_r [\sqrt{-g}] F^{rt} + \partial_z [\sqrt{-g}] F^{zt} = 0$$

$$\boxed{F^{rt}} = F_{\alpha\beta} \cdot g^{\alpha r} \cdot g^{\beta t} = F_{r\phi} \cdot g^{r\phi} \cdot g^{\phi t} = \overset{\partial_r A_\phi}{\boxed{F_{r\phi}}} g^{r\phi} + \overset{\partial_r A_t}{\boxed{F_{rt}}} g^{r\phi} \cdot g^{\phi t} =$$

$$= (\partial_r A_\phi) \left(\ominus \frac{f}{e^{2\gamma}} \right) \cdot \left(\ominus \frac{f \cdot \omega}{r^2} \right) + (\partial_r A_t) \left(\ominus \frac{f}{e^{2\gamma}} \right) \left(\frac{r^2 \ominus f \omega^2}{r^2 f} \right) = (\partial_r A_\phi) \frac{f^2 \omega}{r^2 e^{2\gamma}} \ominus \frac{(\partial_r A_t) f \cdot r^2}{r^2 \cdot e^{2\gamma} \cdot f} +$$

$$\left[+ (\partial_r A_t) \frac{f \omega^2}{e^{2\gamma} \cdot r^2} \right] =$$

$$= \ominus \left(\frac{\partial_r A_t}{e^{2\gamma}} \right) + (\partial_r A_\phi) \frac{f^2 \omega}{r^2 e^{2\gamma}} + (\partial_r A_t) \cdot \frac{f \omega^2}{r^2 e^{2\gamma}} =$$

$$\boxed{= \ominus \left(\frac{\partial_r A_t}{e^{2\gamma}} \right) + \frac{f^2 \omega}{r^2 e^{2\gamma}} \left[\partial_r (\partial_r A_\phi) + \omega (\partial_r A_t) \right]}$$

$$\boxed{\sqrt{-g} F^{rt}} = \frac{r e^{2\gamma}}{f} \left(\ominus \frac{\partial_r A_t}{e^{2\gamma}} \right) + \frac{r e^{2\gamma}}{f} \cdot \frac{f^2 \omega}{r^2 e^{2\gamma}} \left[\partial_r (\partial_r A_\phi) + \omega (\partial_r A_t) \right] =$$

$$\boxed{= \ominus \frac{r}{f} (\partial_r A_t) + \frac{f \omega}{r} \left[\partial_r (\partial_r A_\phi) + \omega (\partial_r A_t) \right]}$$

$$\boxed{\partial_r \left[\ominus \frac{r}{f} (\partial_r A_t) + \frac{f \omega}{r} \left[\partial_r (\partial_r A_\phi) + \omega (\partial_r A_t) \right] \right]} + \boxed{\partial_z \left[\ominus \frac{r}{f} (\partial_z A_t) + \frac{f \omega}{r} \left[\partial_z (\partial_r A_\phi) + \omega \partial_z A_t \right] \right]} = \boxed{0}$$

$$\nabla_\mu F^{\mu\phi} = 0$$

$$\partial_r [\sqrt{g} F^{r\phi}] + \partial_z [\sqrt{g} F^{z\phi}] = 0$$

(A/2)

$$\begin{aligned} F^{r\phi} &= F_{\alpha\beta} g^{\alpha r} g^{\beta\phi} = F_{r\alpha} g^{\alpha r} g^{\beta\phi} = \underbrace{F_{r\phi}}_{\partial_r A_\phi} g^{rr} g^{\phi\phi} + \underbrace{F_{rt}}_{\partial_r A_t} g^{rr} g^{t\phi} = \\ &= (\partial_r A_\phi) \cdot \left(\ominus \frac{f}{e^{2\gamma}}\right) \left(\ominus \frac{f}{r^2}\right) + (\partial_r A_t) \cdot \left(\ominus \frac{f}{e^{2\gamma}}\right) \left(\ominus \frac{f\omega}{r^2}\right) = (\partial_r A_\phi) \left[\frac{f^2}{r^2 e^{2\gamma}}\right] + (\partial_r A_t) \left[\frac{f^2 \omega}{r^2 e^{2\gamma}}\right] = \end{aligned}$$

$$= \frac{f^2}{r^2 e^{2\gamma}} \left[(\partial_r A_\phi) + \omega (\partial_r A_t) \right]$$

$$\sqrt{g} F^{r\phi} = \frac{r e^{2\gamma}}{r} \cdot \frac{f^2}{r^2 e^{2\gamma}} \left[(\partial_r A_\phi) + \omega (\partial_r A_t) \right] = \frac{f}{r} \left[(\partial_r A_\phi) + \omega (\partial_r A_t) \right]$$

$$\partial_r \left[\frac{f}{r} (\partial_r A_\phi + \omega \cdot \partial_r A_t) \right] + \partial_z \left[\frac{f}{r} (\partial_z A_\phi + \omega \cdot \partial_z A_t) \right] = 0$$

$$\partial_r \left[\ominus \frac{r}{f} (\partial_r A_t) + \frac{f\omega}{r} (\partial_r A_\phi + \omega \cdot \partial_r A_t) \right] + \partial_z \left[\ominus \frac{r}{f} (\partial_z A_t) + \frac{f\omega}{r} (\partial_z A_\phi + \omega \cdot \partial_z A_t) \right] = 0$$

~~Revised components:~~

$$\partial_r \left[\frac{f}{r} (\partial_r A_\phi + \omega \partial_r A_t) \right]$$